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Title

Data Hoarding: A Necessity for Early Career Researchers?

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Extended Abstract

Introduction and background

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science has signalled the necessity of openness in research practices. Some journals and funding agencies now also mandate data sharing. In these narratives, open science, including open data, is rooted in principles of openness and transparency. Open research practices are also prompted by the reproducibility crisis and research integrity issues. The dictum “As open as possible, as closed as necessary” underscores that not all data can or should be open; unfortunately, best practices and guidelines are still lacking in many disciplines. Notwithstanding the complexities of creating and managing data, currently open data are not highly recognised or materially rewarded in academic careers. That is to say, data is not treated as important as publications in most, if not all, disciplines. Whether and why researchers should support open data, and how research assessment can be reformed to support open research practices, remain crucial questions.

Our project aims to understand the open research practices of scholars and researchers in the humanities and social sciences. We ask how research assessments can be an incentive for, or a deterrent to, open science. In the first phase of the study, we conducted semi-structured interviews with researchers in the field of archaeology. One objective is to investigate the tension between open research practices and research assessments—a critical issue that has been highlighted by ALLEA, CoARA, Coalition S, amongst others. This presentation will discuss findings about data hoarding and data scooping in relation to the research assessment of early-career researchers (ECRs).

Data collection and preliminary results

Twenty-nine semi-structured interviews were conducted between August 2024 and January 2025. The participants were archaeologists affiliated with academic institutions in Ireland, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The participants are of different career stages including eleven faculty, eight postdoctoral researchers, and ten PhD candidates. The interviews were conducted online and audio-recorded, and were then de-identified and transcribed for data analysis. One researcher has coded all of the interviews and second coding is in progress. In this presentation, we will discuss some findings about data practices related to research evaluation. The findings will be useful for developing best practices and

standards of open data (or research data management) that are discipline-specific, and more narrowly configured as appropriate. Our work thus aids in alleviating the misconception that the concept of open data can only be “aligned with the positivist theory of open science focused on the objectivity of the term ‘data,’ rather than the interpretive and constructive critical theories that are typically drawn upon by humanities scholars” (Arthur & Hearn, 2021, p. 840). This reframing not only benefits the development of discipline-specific best practices, but also research assessment reform.

Data hoarding: Most participants raised the issue of data hoarding in their support for open data. They discussed how some researchers hoard data for a long period of time, or forever, because they want to publish as much as possible out of the data— at the same time stopping other researchers from digging into the data for their own uses. The participants noted that data hoarding is not a good practice in the field of archaeology because data can be sparse and dispersed, as such, the opportunity to collate data to become bigger datasets can be very useful for advancing our knowledge of the past.

That said, many participants did not agree that *all* data should be *immediately* open for many reasons. One notable concern is research evaluation of early-career researchers when they need time and resources to interpret their data and publish. This concern was shared and outlined by Allen and Mehler (2019) in a paper which drew connections between open research, and what they referred to as *The Time Cost* versus an incentive structure that does not yet exist. ECRs sharing their data too soon can be detrimental to their career—because at the moment making their data available does not count when it comes to securing a position, promotion or grant applications. Data hoarding seems to be a necessity for ECRs.

Data scooping: A related concern about open data, not surprisingly, is data scooping, which seems to disproportionately affect ECRs as they work to publish for an academic career. If their data are scooped or compromised, their work could be deemed useless, outdated, or not original/novel—a major downfall when climbing the academic ladder. Interestingly, PhD students seemed to have a more idealistic and optimistic view of open data, believing that data sharing can be a good way to deter scooping.

The consequences of data scooping were mostly raised by tenured faculty and postdoctoral researchers, who are likely more aware of the mechanisms by which research and researchers are evaluated. Those at later stages of their careers demonstrate an awareness of the reality that being “first” is rewarded. Not being “first” can lead to a waste of time and resources and, in the worst cases, an end to academic careers. Whether to share data or not share data, and when, what, and how much data to share will remain critical questions unless and until research evaluation is reconfigured to recognise and value all types of research output.

Concluding remarks: research evaluation and open data

During the interviews, many faculty members use the phrase, “at my career stage” to note their support for open research practices and their concerns for ECRs. They did not explicitly critique research evaluation or suggest that it needs to be reformed, but they certainly highlighted the tension between openness and research evaluation. Research assessments must consider how open research practices affect researchers, especially those in the early stage of their career, and how ultimately, said practices “should not impose extra burdens on researchers” (Ali-Khan et al, 2017, p. 7). It is not just about how ECRs can publish in high- or low-impact or gold- or diamond-open-access journals. For most, data are their lifeline, but open data mandates seem to be coming down without much consideration for how such

standards should be put into practice (e.g. infrastructure, metadata, guidelines, and so on), and there seems to be no recognition of the inequity that may be imposed on ECRs as a result of these mandates.

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